

Awareness, Knowledge, and Attitudes toward the Use of Lasers in Periodontics I Nagpur district of Maharashtra, India: A Cross-Sectional Questionnaire-Based Study

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Abstract

Background: Lasers have gained increasing attention in periodontics due to their potential benefits in soft and hard tissue procedures. However, their successful integration into routine dental practice depends largely on adequate knowledge, training, and clinical exposure among dental students and professionals.

Aim: To assess the awareness, knowledge, clinical exposure, and attitudes toward the use of lasers in periodontics among dental students and dental professionals.

Materials and Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted using a pre-validated, structured questionnaire distributed electronically through Google Forms among the dentist of Nagpur area of Maharashtra, India. The questionnaire was circulated to 150 participants, of whom 99 completed the survey and were included in the final analysis. The questionnaire consisted of awareness-based and knowledge-based questions related to laser applications in periodontics. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, and results were expressed as frequencies and percentages.

Results: Among the 99 participants, 77.6% were female and 22.4% were male. Awareness of dental lasers was generally high; however, clinical use was limited, with 47.9% never having used lasers in practice. Interest in learning about lasers was expressed by 77% of participants, while 19% were uncertain. Formal training was lacking in 83.3% of respondents. High equipment cost (50.5%) and lack of training (33%) were the major barriers.

Conclusion: The study highlights good awareness and positive attitudes toward laser dentistry but reveals significant gaps in formal training and clinical exposure. Incorporation of laser education into undergraduate curricula and structured hands-on training programs is strongly recommended.

Keywords: *Lasers; Periodontics; Dental education; Awareness; Cross-sectional study*

Introduction

Lasers have been increasingly introduced into dental practice over the past few decades, offering advantages such as improved precision, reduced bleeding, better patient comfort, and enhanced wound healing. In periodontics, lasers have been used for soft tissue management, periodontal pocket decontamination, frenectomy, gingivectomy, and adjunctive periodontal therapy [1–3].

Despite these advantages, the adoption of laser technology in routine periodontal practice remains limited, particularly in developing countries. A major reason for this gap is the lack of structured education and hands-on training during undergraduate and postgraduate dental programs [4,5]. Understanding the current level of awareness and attitudes toward lasers among dental students and clinicians is essential for planning effective educational interventions.

The present study was designed to assess awareness, knowledge, clinical exposure, and attitudes toward laser use in periodontics among dental students and professionals using a structured questionnaire.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Participants

This descriptive cross-sectional questionnaire-based study was conducted among dental students and dental professionals. A total of 150 participants were invited to participate via an online Google Form, of which 99 completed the questionnaire and were included in the final analysis.

Questionnaire Design

A structured, pre-validated questionnaire was developed based on a review of existing literature and expert input from faculty members in periodontology. The questionnaire consisted of close-ended, multiple-choice questions divided into two sections:

1. **Awareness-based questions:** familiarity with laser use, observation of laser procedures, formal education on lasers, and awareness of specific periodontal laser techniques such as *Laser-Assisted New Attachment Procedure (LANAP)* and *Laser-Assisted Periodontal Therapy (LAPT)*.
2. **Knowledge- and attitude-based questions:** types of lasers, mechanism of action, clinical applications, perceived benefits, challenges, and future role of lasers in dentistry.

Responses were collected anonymously.

Statistical Analysis

Data collected through Google Forms were compiled and analyzed using descriptive statistics. All variables were summarized as frequencies and percentages.

Results

A total of **99 participants** were included in the present cross-sectional study.

Demographic Characteristics

The age distribution revealed that the majority of participants were between **23 and 24 years**, with the highest representation in the **24-year age group**. Female participants constituted **77.6%** of the study population, while **22.4%** were male (Figure 1).

Regarding professional qualification, **interns formed the largest group (48%)**, followed by **BDS graduates (34.7%)**, **MDS graduates (10%)**, and **teaching staff (4%)**. A small proportion (**3.3%**) comprised undergraduate students from different academic years (Figure 2).

Clinical Experience

In terms of clinical experience, **60%** of participants reported having **less than one year** of experience. Approximately **34%** had **1–5 years** of clinical experience, **2%** had **5–10 years**, and **4%** reported **more than 10 years** of experience.

Knowledge and Awareness of Dental Lasers

Overall knowledge and awareness regarding dental lasers were reported to be **generally high** among participants; however, actual clinical exposure varied considerably. Many respondents indicated limited opportunities to observe or use lasers in routine periodontal practice.

When asked about lasers used for **soft tissue procedures**, **diode lasers** were most commonly identified (**58.3%**), followed by **CO₂ lasers** (**16%**), **Nd:YAG lasers** (**15.5%**), **argon lasers** (**6.25%**), and **ruby lasers** (**4%**) (Figure 3).

For **hard tissue applications**, **erbium lasers** were most frequently identified (**39.2%**), followed by **diode lasers** (**23.8%**), **Nd:YAG lasers** (**19%**), **argon lasers** (**14%**), and **excimer lasers** (**4%**) (Figure 4).

Regarding the **mechanism of action of diode lasers**, **55%** of participants correctly identified the **photothermal bactericidal effect**. Other responses included **ablation of hard tissue** (**36%**), **enamel etching** (**5%**), and **bone regeneration** (**4%**), indicating partial misconceptions among a subset of respondents.

Attitudes Toward Laser Dentistry

Attitudes toward laser dentistry were predominantly positive. Approximately **77%** of participants expressed a **definite interest** in learning more about dental lasers, **19%** reported that they *may* be interested, and only **4%** were not interested (Figure 5).

A strong consensus was observed regarding dental education, with **96%** of respondents believing that **laser dentistry should be included in the undergraduate curriculum**, while **4%** disagreed.

Overall attitude toward laser use in dentistry was reported as **positive in 49.6%** of participants and **strongly positive in 17%**. **Neutral attitudes** were reported by **27.4%**, while **negative and strongly negative attitudes** were reported by **3% each**.

Clinical Use, Training, and Barriers

With respect to clinical use, **47.9%** of participants reported **never using lasers** in practice, **41.7%** used lasers **occasionally**, and only **10.4%** reported **frequent use**.

Regarding formal training, **83.3%** of respondents reported **not having received any formal training** in dental lasers, while only **16.7%** had undergone structured training.

The **primary challenges** to laser use were identified as **high equipment cost** (**50.5%**) and **lack of training and education** (**33%**). Additional barriers included **limited clinical application** (**12%**) and **safety concerns** (**4.5%**).

Anesthesia Requirement

When questioned about the requirement of local anesthesia for laser procedures, **63.9%** of participants believed that **local anesthesia is required**, while **36.1%** felt it is **not always necessary**.

Questions	Responses
Years of Clinical Experience	<1 year 60 %
	1-5 years 34 %
	5-10 years 2 %
	>10 years 4 %
overall knowledge about dental lasers	Highly Unsatisfactory 10 %
	unsatisfactory 10 %
	neutral 38%
	satisfactory 39 %
	highly satisfactory 3 %
laser is used for soft tissues	Diode lasers 58.3 %
	CO2 lasers 16 %
	Nd:YAG lasers 15.5 %
	Argon lasers 6.25
	Ruby lasers 4 %
Laser used for hard tissues	Erbium lasers 39.2 %
	Diode lasers 23.8 %
	Nd:YAG 19 %
	Argon lasers 14 %
	Excimer lasers 4 %

Mechanism of action of Diode lasers	Photothermal bactericidal effect	55 %
	Ablation of hard tissues	36 %
	Enamel etching	5 %
	Bone regeneration	4 %
Attitude towards laser dentistry	Definite interest	77 %
	Maybe	19 %
	Not interested	4 %
Laser dentistry should be included in undergraduate curriculum	Agree	96 %
	Disagree	4 %
Overall attitude towards laser use in dentistry	Positive	49.6 %
	Strongly positive	17 %
	Neutral	27.4 %
	Negative	3 %
	Strongly negative	3 %
Clinical use, Training and Barriers	Never used lasers	47.9 %
	Use lasers occasionally	41.7 %
	Frequently used	10.4 %
received formal training in dental lasers	have not received any formal training	83.3 %
	have undergone structured training	16.7 %
Primary challenges to laser use	High equipment cost	50.5 %
	Lack of training and education	33 %
	Limited clinical application	12 %
	Safety concerns	4.5 %
Anesthesia requirement	Required	63.9 %
	Not always required	36.1 %

Discussion

The present cross-sectional study evaluated awareness, knowledge, and attitudes toward laser use in periodontics among dental students and professionals. The findings demonstrate encouraging levels of awareness and positive attitudes toward laser dentistry, but also highlight substantial deficiencies in formal training and hands-on clinical exposure.

The predominance of interns and early-career dentists among the participants reflects a growing interest in advanced dental technologies among younger professionals [6,7]. Diode lasers were the most commonly recognized soft tissue lasers, consistent with previous reports citing their affordability and ease of use [8,9]. Erbium lasers were most frequently identified for hard tissue applications, in agreement with established evidence [10,11].

Despite reasonable theoretical awareness, actual clinical use of lasers remained limited, echoing earlier reports of inadequate exposure during dental training [12–14]. Strong support for undergraduate laser education aligns with evidence that early exposure enhances clinical confidence and adoption [15,16].

High equipment cost and lack of training were the principal barriers, consistent with earlier literature emphasizing infrastructural and educational challenges [17–19].

Limitations of the Study

The study relied on self-reported data, which may be subject to recall and response bias. The relatively small sample size and convenience sampling limit generalizability. The descriptive design precluded inferential analysis.

Conclusion

The study reveals good awareness and positive attitudes toward laser use in periodontics among dental students and professionals. However, limited formal training and clinical exposure remain major obstacles. Incorporation of laser dentistry into undergraduate curricula and structured continuing education programs is strongly recommended.

References

1. Convissar RA. *Principles and Practice of Laser Dentistry*. 2nd ed. Elsevier; 2015.
2. Pick RM, Colvard MD. Current status of lasers in soft tissue dental surgery. *J Periodontol*. 1993;64:589-602.
3. Aoki A, et al. Lasers in nonsurgical periodontal therapy. *Periodontol 2000*. 2004;36:59-97.
4. Cobb CM. Lasers in periodontics: a review. *J Periodontol*. 2006;77:545-564.
5. Romanos GE. Clinical applications of lasers in periodontology. *J Clin Periodontol*. 2004;31:36-45.
6. Sulewski JG. Historical survey of laser dentistry. *Dent Clin North Am*. 2000;44:717-752.
7. Parker S. Laser-tissue interaction. *Br Dent J*. 2007;202:73-81.
8. Coluzzi DJ. Fundamentals of dental lasers. *Dent Clin North Am*. 2004;48:751-770.

9. Moritz A, et al. Diode laser application in periodontal therapy. *J Clin Laser Med Surg.* 1998;16:13-19.
10. Walsh LJ. The current status of laser applications in dentistry. *Aust Dent J.* 2003;48:146-155.
11. Hibst R, Keller U. Er:YAG laser effects on dental hard tissues. *Lasers Surg Med.* 1989;9:338-344.
12. Gupta S, et al. Knowledge and awareness of lasers in dentistry. *J Dent Lasers.* 2013;7:29-34.
13. Roshni A, Nandakumar K. Lasers in dentistry: a review. *J Int Oral Health.* 2012;4:1-7.
14. Verma SK, et al. Laser in dentistry: an innovative tool. *Natl J Maxillofac Surg.* 2012;3:124-132.
15. AAP Academy Statement on Lasers. *J Periodontol.* 2011;82:513-519.
16. Khan M, et al. Attitude of dental students toward laser dentistry. *Eur J Dent Educ.* 2018;22:e614-e620.
17. Kreisler M, et al. Clinical efficacy of diode lasers. *Lasers Med Sci.* 2003;18:123-129.
18. Romanos GE, Nentwig GH. Diode laser in oral surgery. *Lasers Surg Med.* 1999;25:205-214.
19. Schwarz F, et al. Laser applications in periodontal therapy. *Clin Oral Investig.* 2008;12:97-107.
20. Wigdor HA, Walsh JT. Laser interaction with dental tissues. *Lasers Surg Med.* 1995;16:103-122.
21. Ishikawa I, et al. Application of lasers in periodontics. *J Periodontal Res.* 2009;44:1-7.
22. Midda M, Renton-Harper P. Lasers in dentistry. *Br Dent J.* 1991;170:343-346.
23. Miserendino LJ, Pick RM. *Lasers in Dentistry.* Quintessence; 1995.
24. Coluzzi DJ, Parker S. *Lasers in Dentistry—Current Concepts.* Springer; 2017.
25. Aoki A, et al. Periodontal and peri-implant wound healing following laser therapy. *Periodontol 2000.* 2015;68:217-269.